

The European Commission finances the TRUMPET project within Horizon Europe framework

€ 5 MILLION GRANT TO DEVELOP AN ARMoured PLATFORM FOR MULTI CENTRE HEALTHCARE PATIENT DATA ANALYSIS.

9 INTERNATIONAL PARTNERS INVOLVED IN TRUMPET CONSORTIUM.

ON 27-28TH OCTOBER, A MEETING IN VIGO (SPAIN) KICKED-OFF THE PROJECT.

European Commission has granted the 3-year project **Trustworthy Multi-site Privacy Enhancing Technologies (TRUMPET)** with €5 million. The project has received funding from a **Research and Innovation Action** under the **Horizon Europe framework** (2021-2027) within the program Civil Security for Society. Nine partners, from Spain to Israel, will face the challenge of increasing the security of data exchange protocols in **healthcare through Federated Learning**, an innovative approach that permit **multi-centre patient data analysis** by keeping confidential information safe and increasing protection against possible data leakage.

The project has started the 1st October. The consortium is composed by 9 countries from Spain to Israel.

On **October 26th and 27th**, partners met in **Vigo (Spain)** for the kick-off meeting of the project, which will close in 2025. The consortium is composed by: **Gradient** – (Spain), in the role of project's coordinator; **Arteevo Technologies Ltd** (Israel); **Universidad de Vigo** (Spain), **Institut National de recherche en informatique et automatique** (INRIA - Paris); **IRCCS - Istituto Romagnolo per lo Studio dei Tumori "Dino Amadori"** (IRCCS IRST – Italy); **Technovative Solutions Ltd** (UK); **Time.Lex** (Belgium); **Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Liège** (Belgium); **Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives** (CEA – Paris).

TRUMPET outcome will be a platform that will enable the privacy-protected utilization of multicenter data in healthcare both for research, diagnosis and therapies definition.

The Trumpet project was designed to enable the privacy-protected utilization of multicentre patient data. To this purpose, **TRUMPET consortium will develop a platform based on an Armoured Federated Learning** for researcher and solution developers. TRUMPET will be primarily applied to healthcare sector for supporting healthcare professional both for research, diagnosis and therapies definition. Through the creation of TRUMPET platform, in the future healthcare professionals will be able **to analyse own patient data and comparing it to those of other hospitals and research centre**, by keeping it **safe** and **anonymous** and by guaranteeing **complete patient privacy** as requested by GDPR European policy.

Why is Cybersecurity and privacy protection in Healthcare so important for Europe?

Big Data Analytics (BDA) in healthcare have become **one the most promising approach in the treatment of patients**. Healthcare data collection and analysis from hospitals and research centres, allow clinicians and

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health administrators to make more informed decisions about treatment and services and to increase the life expectancy of people. **Through extensive data analysis is possible to identify early symptoms of serious pathologies and treat effectively**, avoiding the worsening of prognosis. The use of patients' data and artificial intelligence (AI) processes in diagnoses and therapies are crucial for this purpose. On the other hand, patients want to protect their personal information and be sure their data will not be leaked during this process. In the last ten years, Europe has emphasized the importance of this issue (Cybersecurity Act and Cybersecurity Strategy) by choosing to invest in the development of new methods data analysis, while maintaining a high level of privacy.

Horizon Europe is the EU's billion research and innovation funding programme for 2021-2027 with a budget of €95.5 billion. Horizon Europe work programme is based on Horizon Europe's Strategic Plan, which was adopted in March 2021 to set the EU's research and innovation priorities for 2021-2024. Most of the funding is allocated based on competitive calls for proposals, set out in work programmes. Funding opportunities have opened since 2021.